

The Flexibility Paradox: Does Remote Work Improve or Blur Work-Life Balance?

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Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic compelled global confinement, resulting in the swift implementation of remote work policies. Although remote work encourages stable job functions and social distancing, it also poses challenges, including monotonous telecommunications and online interactions, which may lead to fatigue and exhaustion. This study investigates how employees effectively balance their professional and personal responsibilities while telecommuting. The empirical and quantitative analysis examines the impact of remote work versus office work on employees' daily work-life balance by evaluating two independent variables: work engagement and work strain, along with their contributions and effects on employees' work-life balance. The study also reveals that employees' genders, the types of their organizations (private, government, NGO), and their parental responsibilities significantly influence work-life balance and positional conflicts based on these factors. Findings demonstrate that remote work enhances work-life balance, enabling employees to manage their professional and domestic responsibilities with composure. Moreover, work engagement positively affects work-life balance. Simultaneously, job strain adversely affects work-life balance, resulting in a disproportionate work and family life for employees experiencing work-related stress while telecommuting.

Keywords: *COVID-19, Work from Home, Work Engagement, Job Strain, Work-Life Balance.*

JEL Classification codes: *J22, M54, J81, I12, D23*

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Introduction

The COVID-19 contagion has triggered unique economic encounters globally, leading to a significant shift in our social and working lives. Governments worldwide have implemented social isolationist policies to prevent the spread of the virus. It has resulted in individuals work from home (WFH) under state-mandated lockdowns facing various technical challenges they may not

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have encountered before. Workers are suddenly required to use technology in multiple ways to finish their work and communicate with their coworkers, all while simultaneously managing their home environments, which may not be conducive to work. This mandatory shift to remote work (RW) has particularly affected those not previously trained or equipped. This research project aims to investigate, from various vantage points, how working from home affects one's ability to maintain a healthy work-life balance (WLB).

The growing acceptance of long-term RW has had significant psycho-physical effects on employees (Song & Gao, 2020). Despite its flexibility, RW has made employees more attached to their work than during regular working hours. As a result, they may appear to be working less, but the constant thoughts about work and sudden meetings create mental strain. Additionally, technical and communication challenges make RW more difficult for senior employees than their junior counterparts. Furthermore, the lack of in-person interactions and colleague support can lead to feelings of isolation, negatively impacting employees' mental health and job satisfaction. Finally, it can be particularly challenging for individuals who thrive in a collaborative work environment. Therefore, organizations must prioritize creating a supportive virtual work culture to foster communication and collaboration among remote employees.

Additionally, providing adequate training and support to remote workers is crucial to help them adapt to new technology and effectively manage their time to balance their personal and professional responsibilities. Employers should also establish clear guidelines and expectations for remote workers to help them maintain a healthy WLB.

In summary, the shift towards RW has brought benefits and challenges for employees. However, while it provides flexibility and autonomy, it can also lead to difficulties adapting to new technology, isolation, and an imbalance between work and family life. As a result, employers must take steps to support remote workers and create a virtual work culture that promotes communication, collaboration, and the WLB.

Background of the Study

The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly changed the WLB scenario in Bangladesh, particularly with the widespread adoption of WFH policies. While this shift has been a positive development for some workers, it has also highlighted several challenges regarding WLB in the country.

On the one hand, WFH policies have allowed many workers in Bangladesh to save time and money on commuting, resulting in less stress and more flexibility in scheduling. Moreover, RW has allowed many people to spend more time with their families, enabling them to take better care of their health and well-being.

However, WFH policies have also created new challenges for workers in Bangladesh. For instance, many employees have found it difficult to separate their work and personal lives, resulting in longer work hours and increased stress. The lack of physical separation between work and home has also created a blurred line between work and leisure time, which can be challenging for workers to manage.

Moreover, RW has not been an option for all workers in Bangladesh. Many low-income workers, particularly those in the informal sector, have been unable to WFH and have faced significant challenges in terms of WLB due to the pandemic. These workers have had to continue to travel to their workplaces, risking exposure to the virus, while also struggling to balance their work and family responsibilities.

Overall, the shift to WFH policies in Bangladesh during the COVID-19 pandemic has brought positive and negative impacts to the WLB scenario in Bangladesh. While it has created new opportunities for flexibility and reduced stress, it has also created new challenges in separating work

and personal time. In addition, it has left many workers behind who cannot WFH. Therefore, employers and policymakers must address these challenges to ensure a sustainable and equitable WLB.

Research Objectives

This research aims to comprehensively understand how home-based work impacts WLB, WE, and JS. The study will investigate how WE and home-based work affect WLB and the factors influencing WE, such as communication, technology, and workload. Furthermore, the research will examine how JS affects WE and WLB. An additional objective is to explore whether gender significantly impacts WLB. The insights gathered from this study will be particularly relevant in the COVID-19 pandemic, providing organizations with valuable information on promoting employee well-being, WLB, and WE among those working from home.

Literature Review

Remote Working/Work from Home

Whether it's called "WFH," "remote work," "telecommuting," "telework," "homework," "mobile work," or something else, it's the same thing: a way for employees to get their jobs done without physically going to an office" (Bellmann & Hübler, 2020). This work arrangement empowers professionals to work beyond conventional office settings based on remote working. However, remote employees often face disadvantages associated with their in-office foils, such as the community and specialized seclusion (Cooper & Kurland, 2002), unexploited opportunities for unceremonious learning, and reduced company sustenance (Tietze & Nadin, 2011). Also, distant workers may not WFH day to day (Delanoëje et al., 2019). Nevertheless, WFH provides a secure work environment. It also lets workers follow the rules for social distancing set by home and global health organizations like the World Health Organization (WHO, 2020). In addition, WFH has become an increasingly popular option for many employees, especially in the wake of the COVID-19 epidemic. The benefits of RW have been well documented in scholarly sources and include amplified authority and rheostat over job accountabilities (Browne et al., 2019), improved excellence and magnitude of effort (Baruch, 2000), and enhanced employee satisfaction through the ability to contextualize individual contributions to organizational accomplishment in a daily atmosphere (Bloom et al., 2015). Additionally, RW offers more remarkable work plasticity and adaptability (Laegran, 2008), improved WLB, allowing workers to manage their personal and professional lives better (Troup and Rose, 2012), and increased job sovereignty, leading to greater job satisfaction (Jones et al., 2006; Kost et al., 2018). WFH also results in improved individual well-being due to more excellent elasticity in work management (Joyce et al., 2010), an acceleration of domestic obligations (Versey, 2015), reduced traveling time (Kelliher & Anderson, 2010), and fewer disruptions while working (Fonner & Stache, 2012). With such a comprehensive range of benefits, it is clear that WFH is a valuable option for employees who value flexibility, control, and balance in their personal and professional lives.

Felstead and Henseke (2017) and Mann and Holdsworth (2003) found that WFH arrangements can have adverse psycho-physical effects on employees, despite their advantages (Felstead and Henseke, 2017; Mann and Holdsworth, 2003). It is due to the increased effort required by employees, leading to increased stress, especially for those with family obligations (Song and Gao, 2020). Furthermore, RW can blur the lines between personal and professional life, causing conflicts (Vitters et al., 2003). Additionally, working distantly can negatively impact employee interactions, affecting organizational culture (Webster and Wong, 2008).

Work from Home and Work-Life Balance

Due to the COVID-19 epidemic, there was an unforeseen and rapid shift to RW via telecommunications. This sudden change has resulted in uncertainty around maintaining employee productivity and ensuring effective workflow. Telecommuting provides flexibility, but it may affect WLB. WFH can blur the lines between work and personal life, causing conflicts between work-related tasks and personal activities (Palumbo, R., 2020).

H1: WFH does not impact WLB and may increase conflicts between life and work, as well as work and personal life.

Sullivan (2012) contends that WFH improves flexibility in work arrangements and promotes a healthier WLB. However, the benefits of teleworking are contingent on an individual's socio-economic circumstances, making the benefits uncertain. In addition, WFH can present challenges due to the absence of a traditional office environment, such as low organizational awareness, work-related obligations, and the potential for overlap between personal and work-related matters. Balancing family responsibilities and work obligations can be challenging, especially for those working from home. This struggle can make it difficult for employees to allocate time to work and personal life efficiently, leading to conflicts. While telecommuting provides flexibility and convenience, remote workers' use of technology can negatively impact their capacity to cope with the interaction between work and life, ultimately hindering the advantages of WFH arrangements. Therefore, it is essential for organizations to understand the potential challenges that come with RW and provide appropriate support to their employees. Consequently, it is assumed that:

H2: WFH is significantly related to increased employee JS.

Work Engagement and Work-Life Balance:

Prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, several studies examined the psychological impacts of using flexible schedules enabled by advancements in communication technology (Mallia & Ferris, 2000; Bailey & Kurland, 2002). The workers perceived that working from home increased the quality of their work and personal life by granting them more autonomy in managing and executing their duties, according to Van Sell and Jacobs (1994) and Bijssing (1998). Nonetheless, Gajendran and Harrison (2007) developed a model that illustrated the favorable outcomes of telecommuting from home on job satisfaction and productivity while pointing out the potential adverse effects on employee turnover intentions and JS. These studies' findings underscore the significance of understanding the benefits and drawbacks of RW for employees, particularly in the ongoing pandemic, which has significantly impacted the prevalence of telecommuting. It led to the following hypotheses:

H3: WFH has a significant influence on WE.

H4: WE has a significant negative relationship with JS.

Home-based telecommuting has been found to offer various benefits to employees, such as increased flexibility, control over work arrangements, and better WLB (Van Sell & Jacobs, 1994; Bijssing, 1998; Morgan, 2004). However, balancing work and family responsibilities can be challenging for remote workers and require specific skills (Rothbard, Phillips, & Dumas, 2005). Moreover, some individuals may prefer to maintain a clear boundary between their work and private lives, and the potential drawbacks of blurring these lines have been identified as significant concerns (Gajendran & Harrison, 2007).

Job engagement is a crucial aspect of employees' work experience, characterized by high intensity, loyalty, and commitment to work (Karatepe and Demir, 2014). Several studies have shown that increased job engagement is positively related to job gratification (Karatepe and Demir, 2014) and better self-assessments (Lu et al., 2016), leading to improved WLB (Mache et al., 2016). Telecommuting from home is a modern method that enables workers to balance work and personal

responsibilities (Morgan, 2004). Although some scholars have raised concerns about the potential adverse effects of household teleworking on job commitment (Liao et al., 2019), previous research has shown that telecommuting from home can lessen awareness of fatigue (ten Brummelhuis et al., 2012) and deliver superior self-government individual working environments (De Spiegelaere et al., 2016). Based on these opinions, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H5: Employee WE have a significant favorable influence on WLB.

Job Strain (JS)

In today's fast-paced and highly competitive work environment, balancing work and life is critical for maintaining employee well-being and productivity. Integrating work and personal life can result in positive spillover, where positive experiences in one domain can lead to positive effects in the other (Grzywacz & Marks, 2000). On the other hand, negative spillover can occur when stress and different negative experiences in one domain negatively affect the other (Reizer & Freeman, 2014).

One of the primary sources of negative spillover is JS, which has become increasingly prevalent among workers worldwide. JS is a multidimensional concept encompassing psychological and physiological responses to stressors in the work environment (Stanton et al., 2001). Research has shown that high levels of JS can lead to adverse outcomes such as burnout, decreased job satisfaction, and increased turnover intentions (Lee & Ashforth, 1996). Additionally, JS can have a negative impact on personal life, leading to increased conflicts with family and friends, decreased leisure time, and overall reduced quality of life (Greenhaus & Beutell, 1985).

Despite the adverse effects of JS on WLB, there are strategies that employees can use to mitigate its impact. For example, implementing stress management techniques such as mindfulness, exercise, and time management can help employees cope with JS and maintain a healthy WLB (Sonnentag & Fritz, 2015). Furthermore, employers can play a critical role in reducing JS by providing adequate resources and support to employees and promoting a positive work environment (Karasek & Theorell, 1990)

JS has been recognized as a significant occupational health hazard with a wide range of adverse effects on workers' psychological and physical well-being. Studies have found that JS can affect individuals across various professions, including academic disciplines (Kinman & Jones, 2003). It can lead to emotional exhaustion, burnout, and a higher risk of developing mental health issues such as anxiety and depression (Stansfeld & Candy, 2006). The impact of JS is not limited to employees' well-being; it can also have significant financial implications for organizations. High levels of JS have been linked to increased absenteeism, decreased productivity, and higher healthcare costs for companies (Blackburn, Horowitz, Edington, & Klos, 1986; Skakon et al., 2010). Therefore, organizations should prioritize addressing JS and promoting healthy work environments to ensure the well-being of their employees and organizational success.

H6: Job strain significantly negatively impacts employees' WLB.

Research Methodology

Research Design

In nature, the research is exploratory and descriptive. Therefore, the relevant hypotheses were developed to measure WLB among the employees during the lockdown based on the literature and conceptual framework.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

The critical relationship between the variables was carried out using the nonparametric test, independent sample t-test, and one-way ANOVA test of hypotheses. To run all the statistical elaboration, the StataSE 14 was used.

The variables' significant beta coefficient and correlation were measured using multiple linear regression and Pearson correlation. Before that time, Cronbach's Alpha was used for defining data consistency and reliability. Next, data symmetric and normality were tested using skewness, kurtosis, and the variance coefficient, significantly the dataset variance. Finally, multicollinearity or variance influence factor (VIF) was calculated before developing a multiple regression model.

$$WLB = \beta_0 + \beta_1 (WFH) + \beta_2 (WE) + \beta_3 (JS) + e_i \quad (1)$$

Here,

Work-life Balance = WLB

β_0 = Constant of the Model

β_1 - β_3 = Coefficient of the Model

Work from Home = WFH

Work Engagement = WE

JS = Job Strain

E_i = Random error term representing factors other than those specified in the model.

The model discusses a regression model where JS is the dependent variable, and there are control variables, including one called "WLB." The model's constant represents JS's predicted value when all other variables are equal to zero. At the same time, the coefficients of the other variables represent their impact on JS. The model suggests that the effects of WLB are not included in the constant and that each coefficient represents the relative influence of the corresponding variable on JS based on their unique variation.

Sampling Procedure

The data collection for this study was conducted in Bangladesh and included both part-time and full-time workers. The primary data collection method was an online survey questionnaire, as it was deemed the safest and most convenient option during the pandemic. One hundred five respondents participated in the study, with an average age of 32 years. Most respondents were male, accounting for 73% of the sample, while women accounted for 27%. Regarding marital status, 51% of respondents were single, 47% were married, and 2% were divorced. About 38% of the respondents reported having children, while the remaining 62% did not have children. Almost all respondents, approximately 96%, were full-time employees. The data were collected from various organizations, including corporate, government, private universities, public universities, and NGOs. The majority of the respondents, 71%, were from private organizations, while 21% were from universities. Table 1 provides a summary of the respondents' profiles.

Variables

The WFH is considered an independent variable and ascertained that all respondents worked from home during the lockdown. The WLB was the dependent variable and showed how the associated independent factors influenced employees' WLB during the lockdown. Finally, WE and (JS) were considered independent variables and WFH. All variables were measured through 7 points Likert scale, where one was defined as strongly disagree and seven as strongly agree.

Table 1. Likert Scale

Strongly Disagree	Moderately Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Agree	Moderately Agree	Strongly Agree
1	2	3	4	5	6	7

The following diagram shows the relationship between dependent and independent variables and some of the factors known as control variables are considered.

Figure 2. Relationship between Dependent, Independent and Control variables

Gender and the nature of organizations were primarily identified as controlled variables and showed some correlation with WLB. The non - parametric test was conducted to assess their degree of significance.

Data Analysis and Discussion

The research carried out an analysis of 105 respondents from all over Bangladesh. The short profile of the respondents is given below;

Table 2. Profile of the Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage	Having Children	
Male	77	27%	Yes	No
Female	28	73%	38%	62%
Marital Status				
Single (51%)	Married (47%)		Divorcee (2%)	

Source: STATA output file

Among the total respondents, the majority, 96 percent, work as full-time workers, while only 4 percent work part-time. The respondents come from various organizational backgrounds, including corporate, government, private and public universities, and NGOs. Private company respondents account for the most significant proportion at 71 percent, followed by universities at around 21 percent. Among the respondents from universities, 15 percent are from private universities, while 6 percent are from public universities. The proportion of respondents from government agencies is 5 percent, and the lowest ratio is from NGOs, which is approximately 3 percent.

Table 3. Cronbach's Alpha Test

Items	Observation	Item-test Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha
WLB	105	0.64	0.65
WFH	105	0.80	0.48
WE	105	0.68	0.61
JS	105	0.69	0.61
Total			0.66

Source: STATA output file

The Cronbach Alpha value of 0.66 indicates an acceptable internal consistency or reliability level for the questionnaire used in the study. It means that the questions used in the survey measure the same construct and are consistent in their results. While a Cronbach Alpha of 0.80 or above is considered excellent, a value between 0.60 and 0.70 is still acceptable. However, it is essential to note that the reliability of a scale should not be evaluated based solely on its Cronbach Alpha value, as other factors, such as the scale's length, complexity, and sample size, can also impact its reliability.

Table 4. Table for Summary of Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Standard Deviation	Coefficient of Variance (CV)	Skewness	Kurtosis
WLB	4.39	.98	20.7	.13	3.00
WFH	4.05	.72		-0.13	2.50
WE	4.67	.99		-0.11	2.85
Job Strain	4.39	.91		.16	2.61

Source: STATA output file

The descriptive statistics table provides valuable information about the variables' distribution, central tendency, and variability. The dependent variable, WLB, has a mean value of 4.39, which indicates that workers are slightly satisfied with their WLB. The standard deviation 1.06 suggests a considerable variation in workers' WLB scores. The third quartile and 90th percentile values of 5 and 5.8, respectively, show that some workers are highly satisfied with their WLB.

The mean values of the two independent variables, job strain, and social support, are close to 4, which indicates that workers experience moderate levels of job strain and social support. The symmetrical distribution of the variables is confirmed by their skewness values close to 0.

The kurtosis value of the dependent variable is precisely matched to three, which indicates that the distribution of WLB scores is mesokurtic or normally distributed. Furthermore, the kurtosis values of the independent variables are also close to three, suggesting that they are also normally distributed.

The data's coefficient of variation (CV) is 20.7, which is acceptable. The CV value measures the degree of variability relative to the mean, and a value between 10 and 20 is considered acceptable. A CV value above 30 indicates high variability and less reliable results (Brown, 1998).

Figure 3. Normal Distribution Dependent Variable

Table 5. Table of Checking Multicollinearity

Independent Variables	VIF	1/VIF
WFH	1.13	.88
WE	1.11	.90
Job Strain	1.07	.93
	1.11 (Mean)	

The test value of multicollinearity is shown in Table 5 above. Multicollinearity indicates the relationship between independent variables, significantly determining the optimal association between dependent and independent variables. The above test explains that there is no multicollinearity or VIF between the independent variables considered. Multicollinearity occurs if the value tested equals or exceeds 10; $VIF > 10$ (Hair et al. , 1995; Ringle et al., 2015).

Table 6. Pearson Correlation

	WLB	WFH	WE	Job Strain
WLB	1.000			
WFH	0.38*	1.000		
WE	0.40*	0.24*	1.000	
Job Strain	- 0.47*	-0.18	-0.29*	1.000

Table 6 presents the Pearson correlation coefficients, which measure the strength and direction of the linear relationship between variables. The table indicates a weak positive correlation (38%) between WFH and WLB, indicating that WLB also increases slightly as WFH increases. This finding supports the notion that WFH can contribute positively to WLB.

Additionally, the results show a significant positive correlation (40%) between WE and WLB, suggesting that high WE is associated with better WLB. Finally, the positive and significant correlation (24%) between WFH and WE implies that allowing workers to WFH can enhance WE levels.

Furthermore, the results reveal a robust negative correlation (47%) between job strain and WLB, indicating that high job strain is associated with poor WLB. This finding suggests that reducing job strain can improve WLB.

Interestingly, there is no significant negative correlation between work strain and working from home, indicating that working from home does not necessarily lead to increased work strain. Finally, a strong negative correlation (29%) between job engagement and work strain suggests that workers who experience high job engagement are less likely to experience work strain.

These findings highlight the importance of WFH, WE, and job strain in predicting WLB. By understanding the relationships between these variables, organizations can take steps to improve their employees' WLB, leading to better employee well-being and organizational success.

Table 7. Regression Model

Predictors	Coefficient	P Value	95% Confidence Interval
WFH	.36	.002	.14 - .58
WE	.23	.008	.06 - .39
JS	-.39	.000	-.56 - .21

Note: *Dependent Variable: WLB; $R^2 = 0.36$ and Adjusted $R^2 = 0.34$

Source: STATA output file

Table 7 provides insights into the relationship between the dependent variable (WFH) and independent variables (WE and job strain) with WLB. The regression model indicates that WFH positively influences WLB, as shown by the beta coefficient of 0.36. The statistically significant P-value of .002 ($P < .05$) supports this finding, indicating a significant positive relationship between WFH and WLB.

Additionally, the study found that WE positively impact employee WLB, as evidenced by the beta coefficient of 0.23. WE refer to employees feeling involved and committed to their work, even while working remotely during the lockdown. This finding suggests that promoting WE can improve employees' WLB.

However, job strain or work stress/difficulties negatively affect WLB. For example, the regression model shows that if employees' job strain increases by 1 percent, their WLB will decrease by 39 percent. This finding highlights the critical importance of addressing job strain and promoting stress management strategies to maintain a healthy WLB.

Overall, the regression model supports the hypothesis that WFH and WE have a positive influence, while job strain negatively influences WLB. These findings can inform organizational policies and practices to improve employee well-being and promote a healthier WLB.

The research explains its state of conditions to the hypothesis in the following table.

Table 8. Result of Hypotheses

No	Hypotheses	Results
H1	WFH does not impact WLB and may increase conflicts between life and work, as well as work and personal life.	Rejected
H2	WFH is significantly related to increased JS among employees.	Rejected
H3	WFH has a significant influence on WE.	Accepted
H4	WE have a significant negative relationship with job strain.	Accepted
H5	Employee WE has a significant favorable influence on WLB.	Accepted
H6	H5: Employee WE have a significant favorable influence on WLB.	Accepted

The hypotheses and their acceptance/rejection decision are shown in Table 8 above. The WLB has substantially affected independent variables such as WFH, job strain, and WE. But among them, the job strain has shown an optimum significant relationship to WLB. On the other hand, it is often said that gender has a considerable effect on the WLB. It is also confirmed that males have more WLB than females.

Conclusions

The study reveals that WFH significantly impacts employees' WLB during the lockdown. The bivariate analysis indicates a moderate positive relationship of 0.58 between the two variables. The study also considers two other crucial factors affecting WLB: WE and job strain. The findings show that when employees are engaged with their work, it can reduce JS to a certain extent and balance their work-life roles; furthermore, despite concerns about work stress while WFH, the study indicates that RW does not create such stress. Instead, the two variables have a significant negative relationship, implying that WFH can help employees reduce work stress.

JS is found to have an antagonistic relationship with WLB. The study identifies several factors contributing to JS, including technological complexity, new and challenging technology introduction, network and internet problems, and unstructured working hours.

The study also examines the gender differences in WLB, and the results indicate a robust gender and WLB relationship. In addition, the study finds that men's work-life is more balanced than women's, as women may have additional responsibilities at home and work roles.

In addition to gender, the study considers two control variables: organization nature and having children. However, the study finds no significant relationship between these variables and WLB. The study concludes that WFH creates no dispute or imbalance in work-life roles. However, specific factors related to JS can negatively affect WLB.

Recommendations and Limitations

To ensure a positive WFH experience, individuals must assess their personality traits, skills, and career goals. They should also be mindful of the potential for extended work hours to disrupt their WLB. However, it's important to note that the study's findings may only be applicable in the short term, given the limited sample size. Therefore, future research should prioritize investigating the experiences of individuals who WFH to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the impact of RW on their personal and family life. This research can be beneficial in identifying potential challenges and developing strategies to improve the WFH experience, ultimately leading to a more balanced and fulfilling professional and personal life.

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